

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. K. A. Thaker, Head of the Chemistry Department for providing necessary research facilities. We are also thankful to Saurashtra University for the Scholarship to Y.Z.P.

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Solubility Measurements with Zinc Phosphates

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Manuscript received 1 July 1978, accepted 14 September 1978

THE role of zinc in plant nutrition has been well established by several workers¹. The availability of zinc to the plants depends on various factors. Since zinc is absorbed in the ionic form its ionic concentration is the most important factor. Water soluble zinc salts are, therefore, preferred for zinc fertilisation. But the soil conditions must be favourable for high ionic concentration of zinc. This condition is not generally fulfilled especially in soils heavily fertilised with phosphates. It has been suggested that zinc may be rendered unavailable by being precipitated as sparingly soluble zinc phosphate². In order to understand the implications of this hypothesis, it is necessary to determine the solubility of zinc phosphate under conditions which usually obtain in the soil, namely, the pH which may range from alkaline to acid, and the composition of zinc phosphate which may also vary. Moreover, the physical forms of the zinc phosphate may vary depending on the age of the precipitate moistness of the soil and concentration of zinc and phosphate ions, etc.

The different possible forms may be several but those which have been used here are :

- i) zinc phosphate in finely divided condition to simulate a fresh precipitate in the moist state of the soil ;
- ii) a freshly formed crystalline zinc phosphate ;
- iii) a laboratory sample which represents an aged sample in crystalline form and simulates the form likely to be present in soils under long-term fertilization with zinc and phosphate.

The different forms of zinc phosphate have been prepared³ in the following manner :

1) The finely divided form is prepared by mixing a somewhat concentrated solution of zinc sulphate (66 g in 150 ml water) with disodium hydrogen phosphate (57 g in 150 ml water) keeping the phosphate in slight excess. The suspension so formed is dialysed against double-distilled water in a cellophane bag to make it free from soluble salts.

2) About 66 g of recrystallised zinc sulphate in 250 ml water is mixed slowly with constant stirring with 57 g of disodium hydrogen phosphate in 250 ml water. The whole thing is allowed to be heated over slow flame for about fifteen days during which the precipitate becomes coarse-grained. The precipitate is washed several times with water by decantation to make it free from soluble salts. The precipitated zinc phosphate is pressed between filter papers and dried in oven at 105-110°.

3) A laboratory sample of zinc phosphate is thoroughly desiccated and stored in a bottle.

The samples were analysed for zinc and phosphate. The composition of all the three samples corresponds to $Zn_3(PO_4)_2$.

The solubility measurements are carried out at 3 pH's.

About 0.05 g each form of zinc phosphate is taken in well-stoppered conical flasks (treated scrupulously with caustic soda solution and then nitric acid to make it free from zinc ions) containing : (a) 100 ml double-distilled water ; (b) 100 ml double-distilled water plus 2 drops of 0.1N sulphuric acid ; and (c) 100 ml double-distilled water plus 2 drops of 0.1N sodium hydroxide.

Each experiment is run in duplicate along with a blank in which only water with acid/alkali was taken. The bottles are shaken thoroughly in a mechanical shaker for 12-15 hr to allow equilibrium to be attained. The temperatures of the solutions are noted and pH's measured. The pH of (a) i.e. water medium is about 6.65, while those of (b) and (c), i.e. acidified and alkaline media range from 4.95-5.00 & 8.4-8.5 respectively. The solutions are filtered through G4 sintered filter tip under mild suction. The acidified solutions are diluted ten times but the neutral and alkaline solutions are taken as such for measurements. For zinc determination the standard zinc dithizonate complex⁴ method has been used by referring to standard calibration curve obtained by using zinc sulphate solution containing 2.3 μ g of zinc.

For phosphate determination⁵ the method of stannous chloride reduction of phosphomolybdic acid has been used. The calibration curve has been obtained with solutions containing 0.05-0.6 ppm of P.

In the case of phosphorus determination by the above method it has been observed that for full reduction with stannous chloride and development of blue colour there should not be any dissolved oxygen in the solution. The results obtained in the various experiments are summarised in the Table I.

TABLE-I

	pH	Room Temp °C	Zn (g mole/litre) × 10 ⁶	Phosphate (g mole/litre) × 10 ⁶
Zinc phosphate Crystalline	4.95	24	64	43
	6.60	25	3.2	2.2
	8.5	25	0.86	1.16
Colloidal	5.0	34	69	46
	6.65	26	2.4	1.6
	8.5	30	0.87	1.16
Lab. sample	5.0	34	67	48
	6.85	34	2.7	1.8
	8.5	24	0.86	1.16

The results show that the solubility of zinc phosphate is almost the same within experimental limits of error and independent of the physical form of the sample but dependent on pH. PO₄³⁻ ions which, because they have to satisfy equilibrium criteria, will pass on to other complex species. Phosphoric acid is a tribasic acid the three equilibrium constants⁶ being pK₁=2.1, pK₂=7.2, and pK₃=12.3.

The concentrations of PO₄³⁻, HPO₄²⁻ and H₂PO₄¹⁻ at any pH may be calculated with the help of the following expressions :

$$\begin{aligned}
 [H_3PO_4] &= CF^{-1} \\
 [H_2PO_4^-] &= CK_1[H^+]^{-1} F^{-1} \\
 [HPO_4^{2-}] &= CK_1 K_2 [H^+]^{-2} F^{-1} \\
 [PO_4^{3-}] &= CK_1 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^{-3} F^{-1} \\
 \text{where } F &= 1 + K_1 [H^+]^{-1} + K_1 K_2 [H^+]^{-2} \\
 &+ K_1 K_2 K_3 [H^+]^{-3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, at pH 5, most of the phosphate is in the form H₂PO₄⁻; at pH 6.65, H₂PO₄⁻ constitutes 80% of the total phosphate, the rest being HPO₄²⁻; at pH 8.5, 95% of the total phosphate consists of HPO₄²⁻ and about 5% of H₂PO₄⁻.

The solid phase is constituted of Zn₃(PO₄)₂. In solution the following ionic species are likely to be present depending on the pH.

In addition, the system has to satisfy the equilibrium⁷ :

On the basis of what has been stated above the ionic species present in solution at pH 5 are those given by equations (1) and (2), and since equation (4) predominates at this pH no Zn(OH)₂ is formed. At pH 6.5, the equations (1), (2), (3) and (4) hold good and the ionic species mentioned therein are present. At pH's 5 and 6.5, therefore, the ratio of Zn to P in solution should be 1.5. At pH 8.5, the ionic species mentioned in equations (3) and (5) predominate, such that the solid phase is constituted of Zn₃(PO₄)₂, ZnHPO₄ and Zn(OH)₂. Because of the formation of Zn(OH)₂ the ratio of Zn to P in solution will be less than 1.5. Since the stability constants of Zn₃(PO₄)₂, ZnHPO₄ and ZnPO₄ are not known the relative proportions of each cannot be quantitatively evaluated.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Prof. S. Aditya, Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University, Calcutta, for guidance and laboratory facilities and to Prof. S. K. Mukherjee for encouragement.

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Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) with 2'-Hydroxy-3'-Bromo-4-Methoxy-5'-Methylchalcone Oxime

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Manuscript received 13 September 1976, revised 10 July 1978
accepted 8 September 1978

IN continuation of our earlier¹⁻⁷ work on 2'-hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime (HMMCO) as the new analytical reagents for Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) and Fe(III) we report here the solvent extraction studies of Pd(II) with 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime (HB-MMCU).